

METHODOLOGY FOR LINKING TECHNOLOGY INNOVATION TO ENERGY SYSTEM MODELS

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ABSTRACT

This report aims at synopsising a novel methodology to link technology innovation to energy system models. The methodology leads to the development and investigation of pathways for the transition of the EU energy system based on different technological advancements.

This methodology has been developed (and will be further improved) under the scope of the EU-funded REEEM project (<http://www.reeem.org/>). The analysis builds upon the expertise in the field of technology innovation assessment coupled with the experience in energy systems and macroeconomic modelling. The main challenge pertaining to this attempt is the quantification of the qualitative information derived from the innovation assessment platform and subsequently the process of feeding this data into the aforementioned models. What makes it particularly demanding is the fact that the models and the assessment tools have different level of analysis.

In turn, the such interlinked innovation assessment platform and energy system models lead to the development and investigation of pathways for the transition of the energy system of the EU based on different technological advancements.

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1. TOOLS FOR THE ASSESSMENT OF TECHNOLOGY INNOVATION IN REEEM

1.1 The Innovation Readiness Level (IRL)

InnoEnergy has developed IRL tool[®] (Innovation Readiness Level), with the purpose of assessing the level of maturity of an innovation project— especially emerging business (i.e. start up and venture). IRL tool[®] is qualitative and its level of analysis is a project, often an innovative technology or product. The IRL tool[®] empowers analysis of dynamics of innovative processes of a project by considering all the dimensions crucial for the success of a new product/service [1]. Unlike earlier efforts that were focused either on market demands or technology opportunity, IRL tool[®] analyses the stage of project/business ideas in 5 different dimensions. Each dimension consists of several levels determining the project stage in that dimension. The five dimensions are (see Figure 1-1):

1. Technology Readiness Level (TRL): it measures the maturity of a given technology, using the nine levels originated with NASA in the 80's. These are **nine levels**, ranging from the *Fundamental research* up to the *Market certification and sales authorization*.
2. IP Readiness Level (IPRL): it measures the “freedom to operate” of a given product/service. This dimension is made up of **three levels**, which range from the *basic research based on IP Mapping* up to the *detailed and complete freedom to operate in a global framework*.
3. Market Readiness Level (MRL): it measures the maturity of a given need in the market. This dimension is made up of **ten levels**, which range from the *identification of an unsatisfied need* up to the *Business Model definition*.
4. Consumer Readiness Level (CRL): it identifies the level of knowledge about the consumer and to what extent it affects the product/service. This dimension is made up of **six levels**, which range from the *consumer identification and needs* up to the *consumer co-development*.
5. Society Readiness Level (SRL): it identifies the level of knowledge about the stakeholders' interests and concerns and to what extent the product/service impacts on society. This dimension is made up of **five levels**, which range from the *recognition of the stakeholders* up to the *involvement of the stakeholders*.

Figure 1-1 - InnoEnergy IRL tool structure

In IRL tool® the information on an innovation project is gathered through an extensive questionnaire, consisting of questions regarding each dimension and level. Developers of the innovation project fill this questionnaire. Upon completion of the questionnaire, KIC InnoEnergy experts analyse the answers and estimate the project stage in each dimension. The project stage is equivalent to the level in which the project is, in each dimension. The overall IRL of the project is evaluated and reported, considering all the project stages in the five dimensions.

The results of IRL tool® can act as a tool to evaluate business ideas from a new venture and to monitor a project progress in business creation.

1.2 Impact of innovation on Energy Cost: DELPHOS

DELPHOS is a platform developed by KIC InnoEnergy with the purpose to enable evaluating the effect of innovation on the levelised cost of energy (LCOE) across technologies¹. It does so by making a series of cost models and basic datasets to improve the analysis of the impact of innovations on energy cost publicly available. The platform allows industry, investors, the research community and policy makers to make robust investment decisions at a project level as well as to feed their R&D strategy definition processes.

DELPHOS models scenarios for different Final Investment Decision (FID) dates as a combination of technology type² and site type (e.g. site condition) [2]. DELPHOS performs analysis on technologies that are commercially available, meaning that it is technically possible to use such technologies in volume and that they have been sufficiently prototyped and demonstrated to have a reasonable prospect of sale into a commercial scale project. The pre-defined FID dates are currently 2014 (indicated in the following by 'baseline' subscript) and 2020 and 2025 for wind and 2030 for solar PV (indicated in the following by 'FIDX' subscript). The LCOE calculation includes nontechnology effects such as insurance, transmission and development risks. DELPHOS calculates the impact of a selection

¹ <http://www.innoenergy.com/delphos/>

² DELPHOS is available for wind power (onshore and offshore), solar photovoltaic (c-Si PV and thin film), and solar thermal electricity (parabolic through collector, central receiver, and linear Fresnel reflector)

of innovation on LCOE and ranks this innovation in terms of impact, for a certain FID date, based on the formula (1-1):

$$LCOE_{FIDx} = \frac{CAPEX_{FIDx} + OPEX_{FIDx} + specific\ WACC_{FIDx}}{Net\ AEP_{FIDx}} \times nontechnologyeffects_{FIDx} \quad (1-1)$$

Where:

- CAPEX is capital expenditure in FIDx,
- OPEX is operational expenditure in FIDx,
- AEP is average energy price in FIDx and
- WACC is weighted average cost of capital in FIDx.

The data entry process can be divided into three main steps (Table 1-1):

1. *Model core settings*: the general assumptions of the model are specified in this step. These include (a) the global assumptions (e.g. real end-2013 prices, commodity prices, market expectation), (b) technology specifications (size, lifetime, construction contract), (c) site conditions, (d) CAPEX spending timing, and (e) other effects (e.g., supply chain risk).
2. *Project elements*: a baseline scenario is introduced to DELPHOS, which includes data on CAPEX, OPEX, WACC, AEP and losses. In the baseline scenarios, project elements in terms of derived cost and energy-related parameters are also defined. The project elements are included in one of the following groups: CAPEX, OPEX and Energy production.
3. *Area of innovation*: Innovations are introduced in the model. Each area of innovation is divided into several innovation items, and the impact of each item on the project elements for different FID dates is specified (percentage).

Table 1-1 summarises the input parameters of DELPHOS for a sample technology.

Table 1-1 – DELPHOS input parameters. The examples are based on the provided info on DELPHOS webpage for onshore wind technology.

	Input parameter	Example
Model Core settings	Technology type	Wind onshore
	Site type	Average wind speed
	General model assumptions	Non technology effect _{FIDx}
Project elements	Project elements	Development, Turbine, Support Structure, Array Electrical, Construction, Operations and Planned Maintenance, Unplanned Service and Other OPEX, Gross AEP, Losses
	CAPEX _{baseline}	
	OPEX _{baseline}	
	WACC _{FIDx}	WACC in baseline and all the other FID dates should be specified.
	AEP _{baseline}	
Area of innovation	Area of innovation	Development, turbine rotor, turbine nacelle, balance of plant, construction, OMS in wind onshore
	Innovation items	Innovation items for Turbine rotor are: optimization of rotor size with improved material, improvement in blade aerodynamic, improvement in blade design standards and process, and etc.
	Anticipated Impact of innovation	(Presented in % - Calculation illustrated in Table 1-2)

Table 1-2 – Formula for modelling the impact of innovation in DELPHOS.

Impact / adjuster	Range	Value / formula
Maximum technical potential impact on each project element	[-100%;100%]	a%
Relevance to site type and tech type	[0;100%]	b%
Commercial readiness at FID date	[0;100%]	c%
Market share for Tech type at FID date	[0;100%]	d%
Anticipated impact	[-100%;100%]	a x b x c x d%

The results of DELPHOS provide an estimation of LCOE and the impact of innovation on LCOE for requested FID dates [3]. In addition, for a given technology and site type, DELPHOS anticipates the relative impact of overall innovations and each innovation area on LCOE, CAPEX, OPEX, and net AEP. The results are on the European level considering that the current DELPHOS inputs are based on average European data (for example onshore wind power CAPEX is the average European price) [2]. Nonetheless, upon the availability of the right dataset, DELPHOS can provide results on the country level. Table 1-3 summarises the outputs of DELPHOS.

Table 1-3 – DELPHOS output parameters.

Output parameters	Example
LCOE _{FIDx}	
Capacity factor	
Anticipated impact of innovation	In term of percentage, when two scenarios are compared.
Anticipated impact of overall and each innovation area on LCOE, CAPEX, OPEX, net AEP.	In term of percentage for a given technology and site type, when FIDx is compared with the baseline.
CAPEX _{FIDx}	
OPEX _{FIDx}	
AEP _{FIDx}	

1.3 Technology and Innovation Roadmaps

The Technology and Innovation Roadmaps in REEEM are based on the *strategy & roadmaps* elaborated by KIC InnoEnergy. The objectives of the latter are to:

- Select technology areas and develop associated Roadmaps that enable to take action and make an impact in its six thematic fields (for example, wind energy is a technology area within the thematic field of renewable energies);
- Better impact the overall energy ecosystem;
- Improve capacity to generate new products, services, solutions and systems that have an effect on energy cost, reliability or GHG emissions;
- Assess innovation competencies vis-à-vis worldwide industrial and academic energy competitors;
- Attract new partners in the prioritised field.

The *strategy & roadmaps* were initiated in 2011 and are to be kept under regular update in a 2-year time frame. They are developed to identify market challenges and business drivers and to select and prioritise technologies, services, products (i.e., solutions) in order to address those challenges [4]. The prioritisation process is run with the contribution of business experts as well as academics so to assess and then select solutions against the eight following criteria: (1) the Innovation Readiness Level – see paragraph above - (namely TRL, MRL, CL, SRL and IPRL), (2) the highest impact in energy cost decrease, increase of operability and decrease of GHG effects, (3) the leadership and competence of industrial

actors in the said topic and technology (competence mapping/TOP 10), (4) the declared KIC InnoEnergy industry interest and commitment, (5) foreseeable regulatory impact, (6) required investment to develop the innovations, (7) cross impact in several applications and (8) the Total Addressable Market (TAM) or size of the potential market.

Upon selection of these prioritised solutions and their corresponding impact targets, the Roadmap for each technology area is summarised in a one-page overview.

Figure 1-2 illustrates the Roadmap for the example of wind energy technologies.

Figure 1-2- Wind energy Roadmap.

Next, the Roadmap details per selected solution are provided, with the description of five specific aspects: (1) the details per technology or product, service or application selected, (2) the assessment on 'impactability' of the selected solution, (3) the industrial value chain needed (by roles), (4) the actions needed to increase 'impactability' (action plan), (5) the quantitative targets (in terms CAPEX, OPEX, operability –i.e. down time-, GHG).

In a final section, each Roadmap mentions as well the solutions disregarded because their overall ability to make an impact was judged to be relatively poor (based on the eight criteria mentioned above).

Topic	Economic and social impact comments
1. Wind Farm and O&M improvements	
<p>Monitoring Systems:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Smart monitoring systems to assess loads and increase lifetime of WTs • Condition and load monitoring to survey "health" of components. • Software for O&M • Environmental monitoring and actuation package (software and hardware) • New measure systems to improve performance verification, forecast and resources (Lidar...) especially for (deepwater) offshore • Smart monitoring and remote inspection devices (E.g. Remote operative vehicles (ROV)). 	<p>All this monitoring helps to reduce turbine CAPEX and OPEX.</p> <p>Monitoring brings up reliability which reduces costs and increases clean energy production.</p> <p>Criteria: CAPEX and OPEX reduction, life time increase expressed in Cost of Energy for a WF.</p> <p>Estimated overall target: LEC -3%</p> <p>Environmental monitoring brings higher social acceptance for wind energy</p>
<p>Tools:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Weather forecast tools (O&M and energy market planning) • Improved wind hindcast simulation tools for energy resource prediction • WF layout tools for electrical grid optimization and electrical power transmission optimizer. 	<p>Energy prediction improves market penetration and operability. Cost reduction in O&M, energy loss reduction.</p> <p>Criteria: Cost of Energy for a WF. estim. LEC -2%</p>
<p>Installation and deployment:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • New methodologies for deployments (Offshore) • Transport-optimized (floating) substructures. 	<p>Lowering installation costs, which is in offshore an important part of CAPEX.</p> <p>CAPEX reduction target: 8%</p>

Figure 1-3. Social and economic impact of technology/product/service/application selected for wind power.

2. METHODOLOGY TO EMBED TECHNOLOGY INNOVATION IN ENERGY SYSTEM AND MACROECONOMIC MODELS

The methodology focuses on the definition of which technology innovation and learning processes can be exogenously or endogenously represented in REEEM models by proper adaptation of these.

Among the models, a selective analysis was initially made for the macroeconomic top-down model NEWAGE and the bottom-up Energy System model TIMES PanEU.

2.1 Technology innovation in NEWAGE

The *NEWAGE* (*National European Worldwide Applied General Equilibrium*) model is a global, recursive-dynamic Computable General Equilibrium (CGE) model with a detailed specification of the energy sector. Its main objective is to simulate and quantify macroeconomic effects of energy and environmental policy interventions in terms of their economic cost. Due to the total analytical framework of the general equilibrium approach, the interaction of actors on markets of the economy is described in a closed circular flow of income (Figure 2-1). This allows capturing both direct effects in individual sectors (e.g. energy) as well as indirect effects (feedback effects) across the economy that are caused by price-induced supply and demand shifts in response to the political intervention. Figure 2-1 illustrates the concept and structure of the NEWAGE model.

The specific model resolution can be adjusted depending on the analytical purpose. The aggregated version currently covers 18 countries and world regions, 18 production sectors and 4 input factors, as shown in Table 2-1. The EU-28 is composed by Germany, France, Italy, Poland and Great Britain as single countries and the country groups of Benelux, Spain and Portugal, North Europe and Southeast Europe. In addition to Europe, the USA and Brazil, Russian, India, China and South Africa, members of the BRICS group, are also modeled as single countries. The remaining countries are divided into three groups, 'Remaining OECD', 'Middle-East and OPEC' and 'Rest of the World'.

No.	Code	Name	Group	No.	Code	Name	Group
1	DEU	Germany	EU-28	1	COL	Coal	Energy production
2	FRA	France		2	GAS	Natural gas	
3	ITA	Italy		3	CRU	Crude oil	
4	POL	Poland		4	OIL	Petroleum	
5	UKI	United Kingdom		5	ELE	Electricity	
6	ESP	Spain & Portugal		6	IRS	Iron & Steel	Energy intensive industries
7	BNL	Benelux		7	NFM	Non-ferrous metals	
8	EUN	EU-North		8	NMM	Non-metallic minerals	
9	EUS	EU-Southeast		9	PPP	Paper, pulp & print	
10	USA	USA		10	CHM	Chemicals	
11	OEC	Rest of OECD	11	FOT	Food & Tobacco		
12	BRZ	Brasil	BRICS	12	MVH	Motor vehicles	Other manufacturing
13	RUS	Russia		13	MAC	Machinery	
14	IND	India		14	ROI	Rest of industry	
15	CHI	China		15	BUI	Buildings	Rest of the economy
16	RSA	South Africa		16	TRN	Transport	
17	OPE	Middle East & OPEC	Other	17	AGR	Agriculture	
18	ROW	Rest of World		18	SER	Services	

Figure 2-1: Regional and sectoral mapping.

This report briefly presents six methods to introduce technological changes in CGE models for environmental policy assessment. The first method is purely exogenous while the five remaining approaches are endogenous techniques and each one represents a different driver of endogenous innovation.

1- Usage of a Total Factor Productivity (TFP) parameter

The TFP, sometimes also named as Autonomous Energy Efficiency Improvements (AEEI), is an exogenous parameter used as a multiplier of a production function to increase the output, as shown in Equation (2-1) [5].

$$Y_t = A_t F(L_t, K_t) \quad (2-1)$$

Where:

Y_t is the production output at time t

A_t is the AEEI parameter at time t and

F is the production function twice differentiable using labor and capital as production factors.

This approach is already used in NEWAGE model due to the simplicity, good tractability and data availability. However, this solution excludes policy influence on innovation and this can be overcome by either creating several different scenarios for the AEEI parameter or modelling innovation endogenously.

2- Price Induced Energy Efficiency Improvement (PIEEI)

An alternative to the AEEI method is the Price Induced Energy Efficiency Improvement which links price increase to innovation and diffusion of energy-saving technologies [6]. As presented in Equation (2-2), this method utilises empirical evidence to formulate a coefficient for price induced energy efficiency (β_i), related with the relative development of energy prices:

$$\pi_{t,j} = \kappa(y_j) + \sum_{i=1,3} \beta_i \frac{(p_{j,t} - p_{j,t-5i})}{p_{j,t-5i}} \quad (2-2)$$

Where:

$\pi_{t,j}$ is the base energy efficiency as a function of income per capita y in region j

$p_{j,t}$ is the average price of energy in region j at time t .

Additionally, in this case, the method considers only the three previous time steps, where each time step represents five years.

3- Knowledge stock models

This approach considers knowledge capital to be one factor on the nesting of production placed on the top of the nest, as shown in Figure 2-2. In this case, when the stock of knowledge capital grows, the demand for the remaining factors, such as capital, labor or intermediate energy inputs decreases, thus making the process more efficient [5].

This approach represents investments on R&D and is a good tool to measure the impact of policy driven R&D on the economy. Additionally, it is utilised in top-down models and has the advantage of presenting no modelling issues, as knowledge capital is represented as a new production factor.

Figure 2-2: Nesting of production factors with knowledge capital [5].

4- Learning-by-doing and learning-by-searching

These approaches are mostly utilised in bottom-up models and describe the reduction in production cost due to the repetition of a determined process, where the sectors learn how to reduce cost, or by R&D [5]. Additionally, they are grouped together due to the similarities in their mathematical formulation.

The methods are represented by a power function, as shown in Equation (2-3), which depicts the effect of knowledge accumulation as cost reduction of a determined process.

$$C(K_t) = C_0 K_t^{-\beta} \quad (2-3)$$

Where:

C is the cost function that decreases as a function of experience,

K_t is the measure of production capacity installed up to time t in the learning-by-doing approach (but it can also represent the R&D expenditure in the learn-by-searching approach),

β is the learning rate and

C_0 measures the baseline cost.

This method is strictly related to the reduction of production cost and does not capture specific patterns of experience, but rather the average effects.

5- Backstop technologies

This approach consists of implementing a new groundbreaking technology that does not exist at the present time, but can exist in the future. To do so, the modeller is responsible for setting the time step t when the technology will be commercially available and its price, which causes this method to be considered as semi-endogenous.

It is important to remind that in this kind of formulation the new technology will only be competitive if its price is lower than the price of the dominant technology and if the actual time step is later than the starting one of the technology. This generates two sources of uncertainty.

6- Spillover

Spillover effects can occur in several different ways and are characterised by investments in R&D in one sector causing cost reductions in a different sector [7]. The reduction can happen directly due to:

- Lower cost of inputs, such as reduction in cost of engine production causing the total cost of a car to decrease;
- Or organizational innovation being imitated in a different sector, such as lean production that can be applied on different sectors and increase productivity [5].

This method is represented as the sum of non-excludable knowledge that belongs to sectorial innovation activities, as shown in Equation (2-4).

$$\overline{H}_t = \sum_j \beta_j H_{jt} \quad (2-4)$$

Furthermore, the accumulated knowledge is used to augment sectorial production functions, $F(\cdot)$, as shown in Equation (2-5).

$$Y_{jt} = (\overline{H}_t)^{\gamma_j} F(H_{jt}, L_{jt}, K_{jt}, \{X_{ij,t}\}_{i=1}^J) \quad (2-5)$$

In these:

\overline{H}_t is the accumulated knowledge in time step t ,

H_{jt} represents the sectorial innovation activities,

β_j measures the degree of spillover of sectorial knowledge to the economy-wide stock of ideas.

2.2 Technology innovation in TIMES

TIMES is an energy system model which is a further development of the model generators MARKAL and EFOM-ENV, written in GAMS. TIMES is a bottom-up linear optimisation model based on a technical approach. The aim of the model is to optimise the energy system cost according to the given energy demands, energy technologies, and policy requirements. The Pan-European TIMES energy system model (TIMES PanEU) is a 30 region partial equilibrium energy system model. The model covers the EU-28 countries, with addition of Norway and Switzerland. The base year is 2010 and the time horizon ends in 2050. The current structure accounts for 12 time slices, 4 seasonal and 3 daily. The model is split in 5-year time steps. Both greenhouse gas emissions (CO_2 , CH_4 , N_2O , SF_6) and local air pollutant emissions (SO_2 , CO , NO_x , NMVOC , PM_{10} , $\text{PM}_{2.5}$) are included. TIMES PanEU contains the country-specific data covering all the sectors related to energy supply and demand. The system commences from the potential of different energy sources in a particular country and includes public and industrial generation of electricity, industry, agriculture, refineries, inventory power stations and the end-use service demands such as heating, lighting and transportation.

Table 2-1 illustrates the parameters and the units required in TIMES PanEU to characterise a technology:

Table 2-1- Input parameters and units in TIMES PanEU.

Technology	Unit
Size	MW _{el}
Construction time	Year
Lifetime	Year
Efficiency	%
Max. Availability	h/a
Specific Investment Cost	€/kW _{el}
Fixed O&M	€/kW _a
Var. O&M	€/MWh _{el}
CO ₂ emission factor	kg/MWh

The net energy service demand is defined on a sectoral and temporal basis. Maximum and minimum values for the availability of resources or potential as well as optional lower and upper limits of energy use, capacity expansion for a specific technology, import and export activities, mining processes, various cost types and quantities of raw materials can be determined. When there is a flow of fuel external to the model, the prices shall be quoted as well.

Different methodologies can be employed to model technology innovation in TIMES PanEU. These are summarised below:

1. Different scenario runs with different exogenously defined parameters for the technologies;
2. Iterations between several model runs with adjustment of investment cost to the results of the cumulative investment based on experience curves;
3. First-of-kind investment, endogenous learning curve implementation;
4. First-of-kind investment with R&D budget restrictions.

In REEEM, the first methodology will be investigated and applied.

With the existing structure of TIMES PanEU model it is not possible to take into account the global learning curve approach. As mentioned above, TIMES PanEU only covers a certain part of the world. To be able to implement an endogenous learning curve for a specific technology, the energy system model has to be on a global scale. This is due to the fact that the technological learning concept is built on the global cumulative capacity of a technology and the global R&D expenditures spent on it and not on the capacity implemented or R&D expenditures spent in a certain part of the world. Therefore, the technological parameters under the scope of the technology innovation such as investment cost, efficiency and emission factors shall be defined exogenously based on the improvements, R&D budget and capacity deployment for the period up to 2050 in the entire world rather than only in Europe.

Furthermore, to apply the other methodologies, the model would become mixed integer and certain parameters should be expressed exogenously as stepwise functions. With the implementation of mixed integer functions and additional constraints, the operating time of the model could increase significantly. Moreover, due to the additional constraints, the modeller would not have enough space to improve the model under different aspects.

For the proposed methodology to be applied successfully to TIMES PanEU, specific scenario inputs and technology inputs from the innovation assessment platform are to be fed.

After these are set, different scenarios of technology innovation can be generated through a parametric analysis on some parameters for the selected technologies. To give a basic example, if innovation in Solar PV technology is to be looked at, 3 different scenarios could be set up in TIMES PanEU, as shown in Table 2-2.

Table 2-2. Example of scenarios of technology innovation in TIMES according to methodology 1.

	2015	2025 – 2035 - 2045	2025 – 2035 - 2045	2025 – 2035 - 2045
Solar PV Technology	Current state	With low R&D investment	Baseline Scenario (with expected R&D investment)	With high R&D investment
Investment cost				
Efficiency				
Var O&M				
Fixed O&M				
Lifetime of the investment				
Availability				

Additionally, and related to technology innovation, a price elasticity function for the service demands such as heating, lighting and transportation shall be implemented in TIMES PanEU, together with technology-specific discount rates in TIMES PanEU.

2.3 Linking different scales and levels of aggregation

The first step in the design and simulation of energy transition pathways in REEEM was a 'pilot thought experiment', where a scenario with an 80% decarbonisation target by 2050 was set up through a number of models, some of which linked to each other.

The major issue the modelling teams had to face relates to the different time and spatial scale of different models exchanging outputs and inputs with each other. For instance, when a model with regional resolution feeds its results to a model with country resolution or vice versa, the data will need to be aggregated or disaggregated, with consequent loss of information.

Preliminary discussions between the modelling teams identified the issues and first-try options to overcome the different levels of aggregation of the models:

- **Aggregation of technologies:** DELPHOS, TIMES PanEU and NEWAGE may have different technology-specificity. To overcome this difference, the modelling teams proposed to link the models at different stages:
 1. The outputs of DELPHOS shall be linked directly to TIMES PanEU, when the specific technologies are available in the latter;
 2. TIMES PanEU shall then compute the shares of these technologies in the energy production mix. Consequently, the characteristics of these technologies (e.g. efficiency and costs) shall be fed back into NEWAGE as a weighted average on the shares.
- **Spatial aggregation:** TIMES PanEU has country resolution. If higher resolution than the national one is needed, this can be approximated by dividing families of technologies into groups and defining customized constraints for each group. Combined Heat and Power (CHP) technology can be given as an example. As known, there exist different types of CHP technologies with different input commodities, efficiency values and emission factors. In TIMES PanEU, all the individual types of CHP technologies are simply defined as different technologies. For each of them, customised characteristics can be fed by the user. It is also possible to define constraints to limit the installed capacity or power generation on each of them.
- **Aggregation of regulatory aspects:** again, the regulatory framework assumed in TIMES PanEU is on a national scale. If higher resolution is needed, user-defined constraints can be imposed on specific groups of technologies (e.g. emission limits, constraints on the maximum capacity related to limited renewable potential or to opposition by inhabitants).

While implementing this procedure it is essential to harmonise the regulatory frameworks assumed in TIMES PanEU and in other models.

3. FURTHER DEVELOPMENTS

The above described methodology lies in the very core of the novelty of REEEM and thus a significant scientific effort is put in there. It currently describes the state of the art. Taking into account the innovativeness and uncertainty of the outcomes of this venture, we will seek to evolve the methodologies for the purpose of the project to the best extent possible. The solutions for linking the energy models and innovation tools should be considered preliminary and we will seek to evolve them based on the models and tools' potential as well as the project direction. Any evolution to this methodology and/or linkage to the energy models will be described in the reports on progress and use of resources.

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